

DETECTION OF BREAST TUMORS IN EARLY PERIODS AND HEALTH IMPROVEMENT OF WOMEN

Khalikova F.Sh.

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

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One of the priority areas of medicine in the Republic is to improve the health of women and their health improvement.

The most important task of the State in the development of social tasks is the improvement of the provision of oncological assistance to the population and the modernization of the health care system. The government adopted a number of resolutions detailing the improvement of the quality of oncological care, to increase the oncological alertness of the rural population, to improve the work of primary medical care, to bring it closer to the population, and conducts a screening examination of the population.

Purpose of the study: To conduct a mass examination of women in the districts of the region, identified patients with suspected breast tumors, continue additional examination in a hospital and conducts rehabilitation.

Research method: On the basis of the Bukhara branch of the RSPMSTO and R, a detailed study of 801 women identified during the screening examination with suspected mammary gland tumors was carried out in-depth examinations: examination, palpation, ultrasound, mammography, ductography, cytology, consulting an endocrinologist gynecologists.

Examination results: Of the examined 701 women, 120 (17,1%) were diagnosed with a suspected oncological disease. Of these, 12 women

Fibroadenomas were detected, 91 women had diffuse fibrocystic mastopathy, 12 women suspected a malignant tumor of the breast.

12 female patients with fibroadenomas of the mammary gland (node diameter 2.5 cm or more) underwent sectoral resection of the mammary gland, (node diameter less than 2 cm) exfoliation for subsequent histological studies. No cases of malignancy were found. Of the 91 women with fibrocystic mastopathy, 26 women had a nodular form of mastopathy who underwent a sectoral resection of the mammary gland with a histological examination.

Diffuse mastopathy was revealed in 65 patients, conservative treatment was prescribed, out of 12 sick women with a suspicion of a malignant tumor, in 3 patients a malignant tumor was confirmed and sent for complex treatment to a hospital.

Conclusion: As a result of preventive (screening) studies of women, it is possible to detect precancerous¹ and malignant tumors of the breast in the early stages, and this ensures a decrease in cancer, makes it possible to carry out organ-preserving and plastic surgeries, which play a significant role in ensuring the quality of life, especially in young women.

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